

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

Annex I: Economic calibrated models: domain

The following constraints were used in the calibration of the microeconomic model to define the domain of the maximization problem of Eq [1].

-Land availability constraint. The irrigated surface area must not exceed irrigable surface area. If rainfed crops are introduced (e.g., the water allocation constraint is strengthened), agricultural land use must not exceed available agricultural surface area:

$$x = (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n), 0 \leq x_i \leq 1, \sum_{i=1}^n x_i = 1, x \in F(x) \quad [\text{AI.1}]$$

-Water constraint. Already discussed in the main text, see Eq. 6

-Climatic and soil constraints. Each area has specific climatic and/or soil characteristics that favor certain crop varieties, meaning that irrigators' choices are typically restricted to crops that are observed in the area:

$$\sum_i y_i x_i = 0 \mid y_i \in \{0,1\} \quad [\text{AI.2}]$$

where a value of $y_i = 0$ means the crop has not been observed in the area during the time period covered by the database, and a value of $y_i = 1$ means the crop has been observed.

-Crop planting constraints. This restriction sets an upper and/or lower bound to the surface area of those crops subject to a specific policy restriction.

Upper bound:

$$\varphi_i x_i \leq (1 - b_i) x_i^0 \mid \varphi_i \in \{0,1\}; 0 \leq b_i \leq 1 \quad [\text{AI.3}]$$

Lower bound:

$$\varphi_i x_i \geq (1 + b_i) x_i^0 \mid \varphi_i \in \{0,1\}; 0 \leq b_i \leq 1 \quad [\text{AI.4}]$$

where φ_i is a vector that activates/deactivates the restrictions for a specific crop x_i , and b_i is a vector that indicates the maximum percentage the share of a crop can increase/decrease with respect to its observed land use share x_i^0 . In our study, we use crop surface restrictions to constrain changes in the area of permanent crops. Farmers can remove permanent crops, but this decision results in significant capital disinvestments, including through the disruption in the provision of carbon sequestration services. Also, key policies that encourage tree conservation are currently being revised, including the Common Agricultural Policy and the Spanish Drought Management Plans water allocation priority rules. This situation introduces significant uncertainty in the costs of removing trees following a hypothetical water restriction policy and complicates the estimation of an annuity that accurately represents the costs of removing a given permanent crop in the simulations. We apply a precautionary approach and set a lower and upper bound for permanent crops of $\pm 10\%$ in relative area change with respect to the observed land use to represent this uncertainty.

-Crop rotations. The surface area of a given crop or group of crops cannot exceed the surface area of the crop or crops they replace (Gutierrez-Martin, 2013):

$$\sum_{i,j} g_{i,j} x_i \leq \sum_{i,j} h_{i,j} x_i^0 \mid g_{i,j} \in \{0,1\}; h_{i,j} \in \{0,1\} \quad [\text{AI.5}]$$

where $g_{i,j}$ and $h_{i,j}$ are vectors whose components can adopt a value of 1 or 0 to activate or deactivate the restriction.

Calibration of the microeconomic models

Economic calibrated models follow an inductive approach that aims to elicit the parameters of an objective/utility function capable of reproducing observed agents' choices within a domain/set of constraints, to accurately predict future responses to policy shocks through simulation. Noteworthy, each modeling family considered explores one specific functional form for the objective function: additive (WGP), Cobb-Douglas (PMAUP) and quadratic (PMP).

The **WGP** approach used in our ensemble framework relies on the calibration method developed by Sumpsi et al. (1997) to elicit the parameters of a multi-attribute, additive objective function. Note that due to the definition of the attributes above, our application includes a non-linear component in the additive objective function through the risk attribute. WGP allows for both single- and multi-attribute specifications, which makes the approach consistent with the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) (Ajzen, 1991). The TPB argues that decision-making is driven by “the multiple attributes of objects (including but not limited to profit) and farmers' beliefs regarding these attributes” (Pérez-Blanco et al., 2017). TPB's theoretical construct is substantiated by a large body of empirical research on the relevance that attributes other than profit, such as risk aversion or management complexity aversion, have in explaining agent's behavior and choices (see e.g. Gómez-Limón et al. (2016)). On the other hand, use of an additive function may lead to over-specialized responses and even corner solutions: the agent sets the crop that delivers highest utility at the maximum level until a binding constraint prevents further specialization, which often results in a characteristic “jumpy behavior”(Graveline, 2016).

PMP is possibly the most popular economic calibrated model to assess the behavior of agricultural agents, and irrigators in particular (Graveline, 2016). PMP relies on non-linear objective functions to calibrate and accurately reproduce observed agent behavior. Through the use of non-linear functions, PMP avoids unrealistic outcomes such as corner solutions or abrupt discontinuities in agent's responses, yielding instead smooth calibration results (Howitt, 1995). Due to these obvious advantages, PMP has been consistently used to assess agricultural and water policies, including water pricing, in several regions worldwide (Graveline, 2016). PMP calibration uses “information contained in dual variables of calibration constraints, which bound the solution of the original linear programming problem to observed activity levels” to “specify a non-linear objective function such that observed activity levels are reproduced by the optimal solution of the new programming problem without bounds” (Heckelei & Britz, 2005). This is done in three steps: (i) an additional area constraint that bounds the model calibration results to observed choices is introduced in the domain and the dual values associated to the constraint for each crop obtained; (ii) these dual values are used to add a non-linear component to the utility function (typically a quadratic cost function, or shadow cost); and (iii) the utility non-linear function obtained in (ii) is maximized subject to a similar set of constraints to those considered in the original problem, which perfectly reproduces the observed agent's behavior (Henry de Frahan et al., 2007). The main critique to PMP modeling regards the challenge of providing an “economic or technological rationale for the non-linear terms in the objective function” (Heckelei et al., 2012). As a result, a modeler needs to resort to *ad-hoc* arguments to elucidate the outcomes of PMP models following a policy shock (Graveline, 2016). Moreover, while PMP has modeled risk aversion in a single-attribute environment through the use of mean-variance approach, its single-attribute approach struggles to explicitly measure and account for the utility-relevance of alternative attributes such as management complexity aversion. The ensemble framework in this paper relies on the classic calibration method (PMP_1) (Howitt, 1995) and a variation proposed by Júdez et al. (2002), that skips the first step using the average rent of land as dual value (PMP_2).

PMAUP models “build on the axioms of revealed preference to construct a multi-attribute objective function that is both consistent with an observed (and finite) set of choices and prices and suitable as a basis for empirical analysis” (Parrado et al., 2019). PMAUP replaces the dual

variables that would traditionally be added to the objective function to make calibration possible in PMP with agent's preference parameters represented as shares of a non-linear (typically Cobb-Douglas) utility function, the arguments of which are competing attributes (e.g., profits v. avoided management complexity). PMAUP is a data and computationally intensive approach consistent with the TPB that has been used to empirically explore the relevance of attributes other than profit (Gómez-Limón et al., 2016; Gutierrez-Martin & Gomez, 2011), particularly during the last decade, propelled by expanding frontiers in computational power and micro-data. Yet, since only observed behavior is used as an input and assumptions are limited (no engineering-based yield functions, no assumptions of fixed proportions, no limitation to profits as the sole relevant attribute of farmers), the calibration of PMAUP models is challenging where there is a large number of choice variables (several alternatives in the crop portfolio) and cross-sectional variation is low (time-series variation might be confounded with other trends), which may lead to some instability in the model calibration that is difficult to rationalize (e.g. abrupt changes in parameter values following the introduction of an additional attribute). The ensemble framework in this paper relies on the calibration known as the projection method (Gutierrez-Martin & Gomez, 2011) (PMAUP).

Annex II: Accuracy and Calibration results

Accuracy can be measured through two calibration residuals. The first calibration residual measures the distance between observed and calibrated crop portfolios:

$$e_d = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{c=1}^n \left(\frac{x_c^o - x_c^*}{x_c^o} \right)^2} \quad [\text{AII.1}]$$

The second calibration residual measures the distance between the provision of observed and calibrated attributes:

$$e_a = \sqrt{\frac{1}{m} \sum_{i=1}^m \left(\frac{z_i^o - z_i^*}{z_i^o} \right)^2} \quad [\text{AII.2}]$$

The average calibration residual is obtained as the ordinary arithmetic mean of the two metrics above:

$$e_m = \frac{\sqrt{e_d^2 + e_a^2}}{2} \quad [\text{AII.3}]$$

The combination of attributes that minimizes the average calibration residual is the relevant one, and its corresponding utility function and parameters are used in the simulation.

Calibration results for the 17 AWDUs are presented in Table AII.1. Calibration results for PMP models are not reported since they perfectly calibrate to the observed decision/crop portfolio, so the error is always null, and the only relevant attribute is profit.

Table A II.1: Calibration results, attribute coefficient and errors

Source: own elaboration.

<i>WGP (Sumpsi et al., 1997)</i>	z_1	z_2	z_3	e_a	e_d	e_m
2000184	98.82%	-	1.18%	2.82%	8.96%	4.70%
2000185	97.55%	-	2.45%	1.30%	9.43%	4.76%
2000186	92.70%	1.12%	6.17%	2.78%	7.79%	4.14%
2000189	95.54%	-	4.46%	16.27%	4.48%	8.44%
2000190	92.73%	-	7.27%	11.52%	3.87%	6.08%
2000191	97.47%	-	2.53%	4.97%	8.31%	4.84%
2000192	95.68%	-	4.32%	6.05%	12.28%	6.84%
2000193	98.41%	-	1.59%	3.23%	4.90%	2.94%
2000194	94.62%	-	5.38%	8.72%	12.90%	7.79%
2000195	88.13%	-	11.87%	9.27%	9.68%	6.70%
2000196	99.28%	-	0.72%	7.94%	12.78%	7.52%
2000197	97.08%	-	2.92%	1.18%	0.90%	0.74%
2000198	99.90%	-	0.10%	2.78%	2.84%	1.99%
2000211	99.87%	-	0.13%	0.90%	3.30%	1.71%
2000214	100%	-	-	3.72%	3.48%	2.55%
2000330	94.93%	5.07%	-	4.10%	8.23%	4.60%
2000599	100%	-	-	6.54%	11.23%	6.50%
<i>PMAUP (Gutiérrez-Martín and Gómez Gómez, 2011)</i>						
2000184	85.76%	7.15%	7.09%	2.03%	3.42%	1.99%
2000185	81.28%	11.40%	7.32%	4.46%	4.15%	3.05%
2000186	89.44%	3.45%	7.11%	4.15%	4.64%	3.11%
2000189	100%	-	-	11.22%	4.90%	6.12%
2000190	98.82%	1.18%	-	10.10%	2.62%	5.22%
2000191	99.68%	0.32%	-	0.80%	1.61%	0.90%
2000192	99.65%	0.35%	-	4.60%	6.12%	3.83%
2000193	99.67%	0.33%	-	2.06%	0.96%	1.13%
2000194	99.91%	0.09%	-	1.38%	1.46%	1.00%
2000195	99.68%	0.32%	-	9.76%	5.74%	5.66%
2000196	100%	-	-	2.32%	1.31%	1.33%
2000197	100%	-	-	4.15%	4.51%	3.06%
2000198	99.94%	0.06%	-	2.77%	2.84%	1.98%
2000211	98.51%	1.24%	0.25%	0.62%	4.10%	2.07%
2000214	60.42%	22.50%	17.09%	3.51%	3.68%	2.54%
2000330	97.87%	2.13%	-	1.02%	7.71%	3.89%
2000599	100%	-	-	4.00%	2.32%	2.31%

z_1 - z_3 are the parameters of the Cobb-Douglas (PMAUP) and the additive (WGP) objective functions, and e_a , e_d and e_m are the attribute, portfolio and average calibration residuals, respectively. All three attributes are relevant in explaining agents' behavior in both PMAUP and

WGP models, apart from z_3 (management complexity avoidance) that is relevant only in 5 AWDUs in PMAUP and z_2 (risk avoidance) that is relevant only in 2 AWDUs in WGP. Calibration residuals are considered low when the average calibration residual (e_m) is below 10%, medium when it ranges between 10% and 20%, and high otherwise (Essenfelder et al., 2018; Parrado et al., 2019). Calibration residual metrics suggest a satisfactory performance for both WGP and PMAUP models, with low calibration residuals in all AWDUs.

Annex III: Setups and coupling

Micro-economic models and HEC-HMS set up

Since HEC-HMS lacks ecological module, this study has developed an improved ecological module implemented in Pérez-Blanco et al. (2021). The subdivision of the sub-basin units into smaller segments by overlaying the sub-basin shapefile with the integrated Land Use shapefile allows to obtain the micro-economic models agent's crop portfolio and land area distribution for each sub-basin. This Land Use shapefile is formed by combining the Corine Land Cover (IGN, 2017) and ITACyL (2018) crop maps with the Agricultural Water Demand Units (AWDU), employing the Geospatial Hydrologic Modeling Extension (HEC-GeoHMS) (CEIWR-HEC, 2018). As a result, a geodatabase is generated, containing comprehensive information on land use and management for each crop's water needs within each AWDU/sub-basin. This facilitates the emulation of diverse crop portfolios, and its water demands from the microeconomic module within the HEC-HMS environment (see Figure A III.1). Consequently, any adaptation strategy that alters crop portfolio decisions in the microeconomic model will now significantly impact land use patterns and hydrologic processes within the HEC-HMS framework.

Figure A III.1. Schematic representation of the water-human system integration through the ecological module.

The HEC-HMS' ecological module relies on three key pillars: i) The crop coefficient (canopy layer) serves as a general coefficient for each sub-basin, determining the average crop coefficient per total hectares within each sub-basin, with greater weight assigned to crops covering larger areas; ii) Initial soil moisture, which models on-ground net irrigation -the amount of water not consumed by plants- at a monthly scale during the irrigation months (from April to September) that eventually returns to water bodies either through percolation or baseflow recharge.; and iii) River extractions, simulated as river diversions to each sub-basin according to the specific water demand to mimic river extractions as surface demands for irrigation. This ecological module is complemented with the Santa Teresa reservoir management, which accounts for the minimum flow discharge to comply with the ecological flow requirement established by the Douro River Basin Authority (DRBA). Table A III. 1 shows these established monthly minimum flows discharge at the outlet of the two reservoirs in the Tormes catchment, Santa Teresa and Almendra.

Table A III. 1. Monthly minimum flow discharge regime of the Santa Teresa and Almendra reservoirs.

Reservoir	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AGO	SEP	Equivalent inflow Hm ³ /year
Santa Teresa	2.22	2.79	2.77	3.32	3.32	3.44	3.85	3.66	2.50	2.22	2.22	2.22	90.7
Almendra	1.84	2.21	2.13	2.37	2.33	2.22	2.60	2.50	2.04	1.84	1.84	1.84	67.7

Concurrently, water needs for both upstream and downstream regions are effectively regulated through daily flow discharge management. Specifically, the water demand of upstream Agricultural Water Demand Units (AWDUs) is directed at the reservoir outlet, while downstream AWDUs' water requirements persist within the mainstream flow until they reach their designated sub-basin.

Micro-economic models and SWAT setup

In the SWAT semi-distributed hydrological model, the linkage between agent's behavior and the water system is accomplished via the ecological module, following a concept that extends beyond the conventional use of SWAT's Hydrological Response Units (HRUs). When considering the coupling between the SWAT and the micro-economic models, a concept of a "mirror framework" is observed. This framework entails that both the water system and the human system possess analogous fundamental computational units, structured according to common distinctive characteristics of specific distributed areas. These characteristics include factors such as Land Use, management practices, topography, and soil properties, which constitute the Hydrologic HRUs in the case of SWAT (Neitsch et al., 2011). Similarly, for the AWDUs in the micro-economic model, the fundamental units encompass common Land Use, management practices, and economic responses. The challenge arises from the fact that these response units have distinct spatial distributions. In the case of HRUs, they are delineated based on areas with purely physical characteristics, while AWDUs are spatially constrained according to socio-economic or political processes. Therefore, by overlaying these two spatial distributions, a new spatially distributed element is identified, encompassing both eco-hydrological and socio-economic processes, the Hydrological and Economic Response Units (HERUs), which are defined by Essenfelder et al. (2018) as "the lowest level of spatially dis-aggregated entities endowed with decision-making capacity, resulting from the combination of hydrologic units and socio-economic agents".

Consequently, each HERU undergoes individual Land Use alterations in response to policy shocks enacted by economic agents. To depict these Land Use modifications and to accommodate the computational constraints inherent to the SWAT model, a focused approach has been taken. Specifically, in contrast to the process developed with the HEC-HMS model where a single crop coefficient was used per sub-basin, here the ten most significant crops—both in economic and hydrological terms—have been explicitly represented, while the remaining components of the

crop portfolio have been amalgamated under generic crop codes (e.g., AGRL, ALFA, SWHT). Next subsection provides a comprehensive display of the aggregation and code representation for all crops encompassed in this study. Given that most changes instigated by policy shocks result in transitions from irrigated to non-irrigated crops, it becomes imperative to establish distinct crop codes to accurately characterize irrigated and non-irrigated crops (e.g., AGRL-AGRI, ALFA-ALFI, SWHT-SWHI). This distinction is crucial for effectively portraying their respective water management operations. Building upon this point, the configuration, calibration, and scenario simulations follow the identical procedure as that of the original HRUs in SWAT.

SWAT Model

Data:

Table A III.2. summarizes the data source and reference year of the input data used in the calibration of the SWAT model. The reference period used for the calibration is 2005-2013, and 2013-2014 for the validation.

Table A III.2. SWAT model inputs and related data providers.

ID	Data Provider	Description	Ref. Year
Digital Elevation Model (DEM)	Instituto Geográfico Nacional de España (IGN, 2020)	DEM for the Douro River Basin (25x25m resolution)	2014
Land Cover Data	Instituto Geográfico Nacional de España (IGN, 2020) & Instituto Tecnológico Agrario de Castilla y León (ITACyL, 2020)	Combination of SIOSE CLC Corine Land Cover shapefile for Spain (25 ha of resolution) and detailed crop shapefile	CLC (2018), ITACyL (2018)
Meteorological Data	SWAT Global Weather Data (Fuka et al., 2014)	Daily meteorological data for the Tormes Catchment area.	1979-2014
Socio-Economic Agents	DRBA (2016); DRB Hydrological Plan (2016-2021)	DRB AWDUs delineation and crop portfolio in .shp.	2016 (static)
Streamflow, Reservoir & Canal Data	Centro de Estudios Y Experimentación de Obras Públicas (CEDEX, 2020)	Daily measured streamflow, reservoirs outflow, and canal flow data.	1968-2020 (variable by station)

Model calibration parameters:

The following table AIII.3. shows the range of values obtained from the calibration process using SWAT-CUP, for the sub-basins 10 and 11 which pour to the Santa Teresa reservoir, so are at free regime.

Table A III.3. SWAT calibration parameters.

Parameter_Name	Fitted_Value	Min_value	Max_value
R_CN2.mgt	0.206	0.204	0.225
R_ESCO.hru	0.025	-0.003	0.030
R_EPCO.hru	-0.079	-0.111	0.126
A_SURLAG.hru	8.460	8.099	8.649
R_CH_N1.sub	0.393	0.385	0.456

R__CH_N2.rte	-0.336	-0.398	-0.214
R__GW_DELAY.gw	0.820	0.772	0.927
R__ALPHA_BF.gw	0.142	-0.031	0.155
A__GWQMN.gw	2161.824	1903.929	2255.871
A__GW_REVAP.gw	0.116	0.109	0.131
A__REVAPMN.gw	-667.021	-700.907	-661.631
R__RCHRG_DP.gw	-0.565	-0.592	-0.484
R__ALPHA_BF_D.gw	-0.039	-0.062	0.002
R__SOL_AWC(..).sol	-0.449	-0.486	-0.408
R__SOL_K(..).sol	0.139	0.137	0.156
V__SLSUBBSN.hru	94.658	86.777	95.443
R__HRU_SLP.hru	0.357	0.292	0.436
R__CN2.mgt	-0.649	-0.673	-0.584
R__ESCO.hru	0.149	0.132	0.253
R__EPCO.hru	0.369	0.336	0.389
A__SURLAG.hru	1.413	1.271	1.556
R__CH_N1.sub	0.422	0.410	0.671
R__CH_N2.rte	-0.709	-0.782	-0.686
R__GW_DELAY.gw	-0.495	-0.612	-0.478
R__ALPHA_BF.gw	0.93	0.834	0.968
A__GWQMN.gw	-530.709	-538.119	-344.809
A__GW_REVAP.gw	-0.042	-0.057	-0.019
A__REVAPMN.gw	864.581	842.586	896.160
R__RCHRG_DP.gw	-0.694	-0.869	-0.614
R__ALPHA_BF_D.gw	0.333	0.327	0.403
R__SOL_AWC(..).sol	-0.810	-0.815	-0.700
R__SOL_K(..).sol	-0.275	-0.292	-0.260
V__SLSUBBSN.hru	56.139	53.722	58.436
R__HRU_SLP.hru	0.274	0.240	0.346

Table A III.4. SWAT calibration efficiency coefficients values.

Calibrated points	NSE	KGE	R ²
FLOW_OUT_10	0.68	0.70	0.69
FLOW_OUT11	0.72	0.72	0.74

Crop classification:

Table A III.5. Crop classification to be represented in SWAT.

Database crop	SWAT representation	SWAT Code
Garlic	Agricultural Land-Generic (Irrigated)	AGRI
Alfalfa	Alfalfa (Irrigated)	ALFI
Oat	Agricultural Land-Generic (Irrigated)	AGRI
Oat (Non irrigated)	Agricultural Land-Generic	AGRL
Barley	Agricultural Land-Generic (Irrigated)	AGRI
Barley (Non irrigated)	Agricultural Land-Generic	AGRL
Onion	Onion	ONIO
Rye (Non irrigated)	Agricultural Land-Generic	AGRL

Winter cereals	Agricultural Land-Generic (Irrigated)	AGRI
Cherry	Agricultural Land-Generic (Irrigated)	AGRI
Cabbage	Agricultural Land-Generic (Irrigated)	AGRI
Cauliflower	Agricultural Land-Generic (Irrigated)	AGRI
Rapeseed (Non irrigated)	Agricultural Land-Generic	AGRL
Chickpeas (Non irrigated)	Agricultural Land-Generic	AGRL
Sunflower	Agricultural Land-Generic (Irrigated)	AGRI
Sunflower (Non irrigated)	Agricultural Land-Generic	AGRL
Peas (Non irrigated)	Agricultural Land-Generic	AGRL
Green peas	Agricultural Land-Generic (Irrigated)	AGRI
Dry Beans	Agricultural Land-Generic (Irrigated)	AGRI
Lettuce	Agricultural Land-Generic (Irrigated)	AGRI
Lentils (Non irrigated)	Agricultural Land-Generic (Irrigated)	AGRI
Corn	Corn	CORN
Fodder corn	Agricultural Land-Generic (Irrigated)	AGRI
Apple tree	Agricultural Land-Generic (Irrigated)	AGRI
Apple tree (Non irrigated)	Agricultural Land-Generic	AGRL
Melon	Agricultural Land-Generic (Irrigated)	AGRI
Other grasses	Agricultural Land-Generic	AGRL
Potato	Potato	POTA
Pear tree	Agricultural Land-Generic (Irrigated)	AGRI
Pepper	Agricultural Land-Generic (Irrigated)	AGRI
Polyphytic meadows	Pasture	PAST
Beetroot	Sugarbeet	SGBT
Watermelon	Agricultural Land-Generic (Irrigated)	AGRI
Tomato	Tomato	TOMA
Wheat	Spring Wheat (Irrigated)	SWHI
Wheat (Non irrigated)	Spring Wheat	SWHT
Vallico	Agricultural Land-Generic (Irrigated)	AGRI
Vetch	Agricultural Land-Generic (Irrigated)	AGRI
Vetch for fodder	Agricultural Land-Generic (Irrigated)	AGRI

HEC-HMS Model

Data:

The databases and data providers used for HEC-HMS are identical to those listed for SWAT (Table AIII.2). The calibration process aligns with the reference period spanning from 1996 to 2013.

Model calibration parameters:

The following table A III.6. shows the range of values obtain from the calibration process using a maximization goal focus on the Nash–Sutcliffe coefficient objective, for the sub-basins 10 and 11 which pour to the Santa Teresa reservoir, so are at free regime.

Table A III.6. HEC-HMS calibration parameters.

Calibration - J130

Sub-basin	Parameter	Units	Initial Value	Optimized Value
W950	Linear Reservoir - GW 1 Coefficient (1)	HR	353,57	8938,60
W950	Linear Reservoir - GW 1 Initial Discharge (1)	M3/S	0,56	3,44
W950	SCS Unit Hydrograph - Lag Time	MIN	120,23	9737,50
W950	Simple Canopy - Initial Storage	%	1,28	4,26
W950	Simple Canopy - Max Storage	MM	1,23	2,30
W950	Simple Surface - Initial Storage	%	1,59	1,52
W950	Simple Surface - Max Storage	MM	1,22	0,81
W950	Soil Moisture Accounting - GW1 Percolation	MM/HR	15,42	6,74
W950	Soil Moisture Accounting - GW1 Storage	MM	700,09	286,24
W950	Soil Moisture Accounting - GW1 Storage Coefficient	HR	550,48	127,06
W950	Soil Moisture Accounting - GW2 Percolation	MM/HR	7,82	1,40
W950	Soil Moisture Accounting - GW2 Storage	MM	970,99	125,98
W950	Soil Moisture Accounting - GW2 Storage Coefficient	HR	595,26	67,15
W950	Soil Moisture Accounting - Initial GW1 Content	%	0,39	0,12
W950	Soil Moisture Accounting - Initial GW2 Content	%	0,36	0,04
W950	Soil Moisture Accounting - Initial Soil Content	%	0,42	0,03
W950	Soil Moisture Accounting - Max Infiltration	MM/HR	5,52	2,60
W950	Soil Moisture Accounting - Soil Percolation	MM/HR	4,48	
	Soil Moisture Accounting - Soil Storage	MM	277,82	
	Soil Moisture Accounting - Tension Storage	MM	2,66	0,57
W960	Linear Reservoir - GW 1 Coefficient (1)	HR	353,57	259,30
W960	Linear Reservoir - GW 1 Initial Discharge (1)	M3/S	0,56	0,04
W960	SCS Unit Hydrograph - Lag Time	MIN	120,23	431,90
W960	Simple Canopy - Initial Storage	%	1,28	0,51
W960	Simple Canopy - Max Storage	MM	1,23	0,27
W960	Simple Surface - Initial Storage	%	1,59	0,22
W960	Simple Surface - Max Storage	MM	1,22	0,10
W960	Soil Moisture Accounting - GW1 Percolation	MM/HR	15,42	0,84
W960	Soil Moisture Accounting - GW1 Storage	MM	700,09	111,40
W960	Soil Moisture Accounting - GW1 Storage Coefficient	HR	550,48	33,78
W960	Soil Moisture Accounting - GW2 Percolation	MM/HR	7,82	0,63
W960	Soil Moisture Accounting - GW2 Storage	MM	970,99	54,51
W960	Soil Moisture Accounting - GW2 Storage Coefficient	HR	595,26	28,70
W960	Soil Moisture Accounting - Initial GW1 Content	%	0,39	0,19
W960	Soil Moisture Accounting - Initial GW2 Content	%	0,36	0,12
W960	Soil Moisture Accounting - Initial Soil Content	%	0,42	0,10
W960	Soil Moisture Accounting - Max Infiltration	MM/HR	5,52	0,01
W960	Soil Moisture Accounting - Soil Percolation	MM/HR	4,48	2,16
W960	Soil Moisture Accounting - Soil Storage	MM	277,82	26,79
W960	Soil Moisture Accounting - Tension Storage	MM	2,66	0,69

Table A III.7. HEC-HMS calibration efficiency coefficients values.

Calibrated points	NSE	Log NSE	RMSE	R²
W 1060	0.42	0.62	0.8	0.44
J 130	0.50	0.57	0.7	0.59